

PEDAGOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL AND PERSONAL QUALITIES OF A PRIMARY CLASS TEACHER

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Abstract. *In the article of primary school teachers professional and personal qualities development factors its significance as a scientific-pedagogical problem has been studied. The theoretical and pedagogical aspects of the development of professional and personal qualities of primary school teachers are scientifically based. The correct organization of professional-methodical activities, guidelines for the formation of professional and personal qualities are discussed.*

Keywords: *professional, pedagogue, modern teacher, self-development, self-improvement, personal qualities, component.*

A teacher is a profession that is always in demand. This is a type of activity that is discussed and appreciated by all. So, what should be a good teacher today? A real professional modern teacher is, first of all, a skilled teacher. He performs the main task of his profession perfectly. This is a person who is given to teach others. A good teacher gives children an excellent quality - the ability to know the world and develop. It teaches perception, processing and independent application of information. This can only be achieved by a teacher who has the following characteristics:

- loves children and is interested in them;
- can enter the inner world of children;
- knows the psychology of schoolchildren of different ages;
- appreciates the uniqueness of the child's personality;
- can observe children's behavior and make conclusions;
- can assess the intellectual potential and create a child's individual development strategy;
- easily communicates with children, earns their love and respect;
- successfully manages the children's team;
- knows his subject in depth and can convey it;
- is ready for innovation in his field and strives for development.

A teacher performs many functions in the process of pedagogical activity. The success of these functions is determined by the teacher's personality and professional qualities. The peculiarity of pedagogical work imposes a number of requirements for him, for his personality, which are called professionally important personal qualities.

Attempts to develop a list of personal and professional qualities of primary school teachers have a long history. Writer, journalist and book publisher N.I. Novikov said that the educator must meet the following requirements;

- to have the ability to think correctly and clearly;
- be able to address children;
- to be kind, to pronounce foreign languages well;

good manners and good appearance.

K. D. Ushinsky firmly emphasized that "in every teacher, especially teachers assigned to lower schools and public schools, not only teaching, but also character, morals and faith are important..."

The ideal model of a teacher, class leader, student is a model, a standard that presents the basic personal characteristics that a teacher should have;

secondly, it is the knowledge, abilities, skills and professional profile for performing the functions of a teacher.

Professiogram is a description of professions and specialties that classify them in terms of the requirements imposed on a person by the profession.

Pedagogical professionogram - young people who are preparing for pedagogical activity should know the features of the specialization listed in the pedagogical professionogram. The professionogram includes the following features:

1. characteristics of the teacher's personality;
2. requirements for the teacher's mental and pedagogical preparation;
3. scope and content of special training;
4. The content of methodological preparation for the specialty.

Based on this concept of meaning, we can talk about the professionographic method of studying a person, in which the teacher's knowledge, skills and abilities are compared with what he can be in accordance with the ideal model. It is not difficult to imagine that this method allows to design the personal and professional growth of the teacher. At the same time, the teacher's professional profile is a document that gives a complete qualification characteristic to the teacher in terms of his knowledge, skills and abilities, his personality, abilities, psychophysiological capabilities and requirements for the level of training.

The need to create a professional profile for a modern teacher is determined by a number of reasons:

importance of social order for school, teaching profession;
society's growing demands on the personality of the teacher;
changes in the criteria of his professional competences in connection with social and scientific-technical changes.

The professional pedagogical direction of a teacher includes the following components:

1. Love for children, interest in profession, creativity related to education of human qualities in them;
2. To be aware of difficulties and problems in teaching;
3. The need for teaching activities;
4. To realize one's capabilities and abilities in accordance with the requirements of the chosen profession;
5. The need for constant self-improvement and striving to master the basics of pedagogical skills.

Professionally important qualities of a teacher are the characteristics of the mental, emotional-volitional and moral aspects of a person, which affect the effectiveness (success) of the teacher's professional and pedagogical activity and determine his individual style. The most important professional aspects of the modern teacher model are reflected.

Citizenship (social responsibility, willingness of a person to make an active, enthusiastic contribution to solving social problems);

Love for children (humanity, benevolence, sensitivity, attentiveness, sincerity, politeness, etc.);

Optimism (belief in the power and possibilities of positive development of the student);

Justice (honesty, conscientiousness, ability to act impartially);

Solidarity (pedagogical tact, community);

Altruism - selflessness (concern for the well-being of others);

Strong-willed qualities (endurance, self-control, restraint, fortitude, strength, determination, patience, courage);

The group of communication skills includes sensory skills, which are skills that manifest themselves at the initial stage of communication, the ability to understand other people (students, teachers, parents), as well as pedagogical communication skills and skills and abilities of pedagogical techniques (the ability to choose the right style) and tone, control attention, sense of speed, develop speech culture, control your body, regulate your mental state, etc.

Pedagogical skill - the highest level of professionalism - is born on the basis of the combination of personal qualities and professional competence of primary school teachers.

Being a master of pedagogical work means a deep understanding of the laws of education and training, skillful application of them in practice, and achieving clear results in the development of the personality of an educated person.

1. Training courses. Currently, such courses are an important and main stage of teacher's self-development, a unique method. Such courses are usually led by the head of the educational institution;

2. There are also federal standards that state that every teacher must create a self-development program at the beginning of this year. This program has been in development for over a year and includes setting clear goals, highlighting the theme of self-development. Also, the teacher shows the literature he uses in the process of self-development and determines the conclusions of his work.

It can be seen that the main task of a modern teacher is to study information in depth, which can later become the basis for increasing the level of qualifications and general professional skills.

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